

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B045
 Date: 29 Aug 2004
 Take Off 07:58:59
 Landing: 12:58:41
 Flight Time 4h59m42

Trials Instructions: ADRIEX – flight to investigate pollution in the Po Valley, Italy
Operating Area: Po Valley, N Italy

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Co-pilot 2	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Ellie Highwood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
8	TDL / WAS / PAN / Tubes	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
10	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
11	Filters	Paola Formenti	CNRS/University of Paris 12
12	AMS	Hugh Coe	UMIST
13	VACC	Stuart Heath	FAAM
14	Mission Scientist 2	Simon Osborne	Met Office
15	Mission Scientist 3	Nicolas Bellouin	Met Office
16	Mission Scientist 3	Jolene Cook	Reading University
17	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
18			
19			

Flight Track:

B045 Track 29-AUG-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B045
 Date: 29/08/04
 Project: ADRIEX
 Location: Po Valley

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
075859		T/O	4.9 kft	131	Treviso
080808		Videos	4.9 kft	130	Start Recording
081256	081616	Profile 1	4.9 - 3.0 kft	215	
081846	081950	Profile 2	3.0 - 3.9 kft	204	
082001	082809	Run 1.1	4.0 - 3.9 kft	204	A to B
082942	084608	Run 1.2	3.9 kft	336	B to C
084815	090258	Run 1.3	3.9 kft	222	C to D
090509	091935	Run 1.4	3.9 kft	358	D to E
092303	093419	Profile 3	3.9 - 15.0 kft	155	E to D, 1000fpm
093935	094924	Profile 4	15.0 - 3.0 kft	034	D to C, Interrupt
095308	095424	Profile 4	2.9 kft	335	
095425	100952	Run 2.1	2.9 kft	335	C to B
101107	102322	Run 2.2	2.9 - 3.0 kft	335	B to A
102322	102441	Profile 5	2.9 kft	334	
103404	104816	Run 3.1	3.0 kft	335	A to B
105019	105300	Run 3.2	3.0 kft		B to C
105300	105632	Profile 6	5.0 - 3.0 kft	334	
105748	110516	Run 3.3	2.9 kft	334	
110823	112207	Run 3.4	2.9 kft	335	C to D
112414	113657	Run 3.5	2.9 kft	335	D to E
114052	115336	Profile 7	2.9 - 15.0 kft	146	at Delta
115832	120936	Profile 8	15.0 - 3.0 kft	039	D to C
121248	122958	Run 4.1	2.9 - 3.0 kft	145	C o B
123131	124426	Run 4.2	3.0 kft	020	B to A
125841		Land	0.00 kft	339	Treviso
140159		UBBRs	0.00 kft	359	Covered

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B045 Track 29-AUG-04

FAAM Sortie Brief

Flight Number: B045

Date: Sunday 29th August

Purpose: ADRIEX flight to investigate pollution in the Po Valley, Italy.

Weather: Predominantly cloud-free. Heavy pollution preferred.

Flight Pattern:

- 1) Take off Treviso 08:00Z.
- 2) Transit to point A, (45°18'51"N,12°30'29"E) (15mins).
- 3) SLR at 3000ft from A to point B (44°30'N,12°00'E) (30mins).
- 4) SLR at 3000ft from B to point C at Soave (45°25'N,11°15'E) (50mins).
- 5) SLR at 3000ft from C to point D at Reggio Nell Emilia (44°42'N,10°32'E) (65mins).
- 6) SLR at 3000ft from from D to point E at (45°30'N,10°00'E) (80mins).
- 7) Profile ascent to FL150 from point E to point D (95mins).
- 8) Profile descent from FL150 to 3000ft from point D to point C (110mins) .
- 9) SLR at 3000ft from point C to point B (130mins).
- 10) SLR at 3000ft from point B to point A (145mins).
- 11) Repeat 3-10 (290mins).
- 12) If time permits, perform a series of sampling runs within the aerosol plume.

Point A (Ocean Tower)	45°18'51"N,12°30'29"E
Point B	44°30'N,12°00'E
Point C (Soave)	45°25'N,11°15'E
Point D (Reggio Nell Emilia)	44°42'N,10°32'E
Point E	45°30'N,10°00'E

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B045

Date: 29th August 2004

Sortie Objectives: ADRIEX flight #3. To investigate the pollution up the Po Valley using in-situ measurements for comparison with ADRIEX flight #1.

Operating area: Po Valley and ocean areas over the northern Adriatic Ocean. 5 points were defined:-

A:-	Ocean Tower	45°18'51''N, 12°30'29'E
B:-		44°30'N, 12°00'E
C:-	Soave	45°25'N, 11°15'E
D:-	Reggio Nell Emilia	44°42'N, 10°32'E
E:-		44°30'N, 10°00'E

Weather: Extensive contrails and cirrus particularly at the start of the flight. During the first half of the flight, cloud top was around 3000ft along the Po Valley. During the second half, Cu extended between approx 4000-7000ft. Scattered Cu increased towards the north side of the valley, as did the pollution. Two pollution layers clearly visible, one above, and one below cloud level. Should compare this with B043.

Flight Patterns:

Take off from Treviso at ~08:00. Transit to point A at 5000ft. Profile descent to 3000ft towards point B on the first leg of the zig-zag up the Po Valley. The first run was interrupted and ascent necessary to 4000ft to avoid cloud. The remainder of the zig-zag pattern was then performed at 4000ft up the Po Valley from point A->B->C->D->E. The aircraft was above the boundary layer for the duration of these legs and a fairly extensive aerosol layer was evident above the cloud, particularly towards the northern side of the valley. CN and neph showed variation in aerosol concentration, but AMS showed more homogeneity in constituents. Various local pollution sources were also detected by AMS and nephelometer. At the ocean tower at point A, a profile ascent to 5000ft allowed pilot change-over. A profile descent was then performed to 3000ft, to below the Sc Cu and towards point B. The zig-zag pattern A->B->C->D-> was repeated at 3000ft. Conditions alternated between clear and Sc Cu below. High NO and CN counts of 91000 observed during these runs. Peaks in CO and neph observed at turn at point E over the motorway. A reciprocal heading was then flown down the Po Valley from E->D->C->B->A with a profile ascent/descent 4000ft-FL150-4000ft from E->D and from D->C, the remainder being at 3000ft.

Summary:

A successful flight in more polluted conditions than B043. Aerosol optical depths were higher over the Adriatic than previously throughout the day, being 0.3 in the morning and 0.15 in the afternoon (Nicelli Airport) AERONET and 0.15 at ISDGM in the afternoon. Local fresh pollution was measured up the Po Valley. Uncorrected single scattering albedo reached ~0.87 in the lower pollution layer, but due to problems with both neph and psap, this cannot be considered reliable.

Problems:

Nephelometer failed again part way through the flight, and was intermittent. PSAP front display is still showing different values to those on Horace. PCASP (wing mounted) is missing the first three channels.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B045

Date: 28th August 2004

Sortie Objectives: ADRIEX flight #3. To investigate the pollution up the Po Valley using in-situ measurements for comparison with ADRIEX flight #1.

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A:-	Ocean Tower	45°18'51''N, 12°30'29'E
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Intermittent problems with HORACE displaying
new plots & windows including on flight manager
& aircraft scientist displays. Related to no. of
display windows open?

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.045**.....

 Date 29/8/04.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
080000		Take off Treviño		Treviño Airport	Widespread cirrus, contrasts visible <i>extensive</i>
					Cu to left of runway on t/off e right esp over high ground
					Mountains obscured, heavy pollution layer capped by Cu to left of take off
					Bio smoke ^{small fires} on ground to left as turning Some Cu below
080433					Cu below on left ^{right} , Ci only on left
080807					Over Sea Sc Cu below, 8/8 Ci above Co up to 180 ppb in bottom 400m
081232		5000ft			Pollution layer below visible
081258	P1	5000 ↓			Sc Cu below & to right
081359		4500 ↓			Pass over change in ocean colour Contrails
081619					Cloud @ min level
081616	P1	3000ft			Neph off.
081858	P2A	3400			In cloud
08	P2	4000ft			Above cloud ..
082134					O ₃ 67, CO, 120
082422					CO calibrating 120-136 ppm <i>ppb</i>
082829	end of R10				Right turn, above pollution
082931					
082941	R2	4000ft			Neph up, change in ratio
083600		4000ft			Cu below
083806		4000ft			Reads 6, HORACE 2 e-6.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.045**
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Date

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
083932		4000ft			wo uncor 0.89 using PSAP dial 0.98 reading HORACE! Cu below
08424		4000ft			PSAPS 4-500 Neph up Clear below, Cu to left/right Sc Cu & contrails above
08438A					
08					O ₃ high - photochem
08 465					Filters? uncorrected
084608	R1.2				Structure in neph, a/c, CO, O ₃
084815	R1.3	4000ft			clear below, contrails, Ci
085125	R1.3				Cloud below Sc. 2½ mg m ⁻³ , sulphate change in aerosol AMS @ point C + ammonium nitrate
08525	R1.3	4000ft			cloud below, nephs dropped off. CO 140.41 ppb.
085350	R1.3	4000ft			Bumps, some Cu extending to this level.
085540	R1.3	4000ft			cloud top lower, but still Sc Cu Pollution visible to left to right, Ci to left.
085659	R1.3	4000ft			thin pollution layer to right, clear slot below. ^{? Poll} Becoming thinner ahead
085825	R1.3				Poss elevated pollution layer to North clear slot (in which we are), then some lower. Mainly clear below, Sc Cu.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
090057	R1.3	4000ft			Pollution to north visible. otherwise uniform clear below
090256	R1.3	4000ft			Clear below, enforced inside turn
090506	R1.4	4000ft	S-E		Clear below, 2 pollution layers vis, ahead, with clear slot in between. Top layer above Sc Cu
090836	R1.4	4000ft			Approaching thick pollution layer above & below cloud top. Above cloud clearly visible
090954	R1.4	4000ft			CO dropping off rapidly
091139					CO & neph dropping off - in clean slot
091243	R1.4	4000ft			Sc Cu below, in clean slot Layers above & below
091547	R1.4	4000ft			Extensive Cu below, clean slot visible above cloud top, level with
091742	R1.4				
091742	R1.4	4000ft			Some peaks on CO but still low Sc Cu below, Ci above
091853	R1.4				neph & low sharp line in CO, AC, & neph, entering pollution, clear air below.
091938	and R1.4	4000ft			Clear below Cloud above 6/8
092303	P2	4000ft ↑			Clear below Cloud above
092514	P2	6000ft ↑			Ext Sc Cu below, Ci above Double pollution layer still vis
092650		6500ft			CO, Neph ↓ quickly top of aerosol layer

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
092816	P3 ↑	9000ft			Ex Cu below, to left, clear below
092957	↑	10000ft			to right. Largely clear above
0	orig P3				CO & neph structure well correlated
093528	P3	15000ft			in pollution layer. Well defined
093800		15000ft			CO calibration start.
093934	P4 ↓	15000ft			CO calibration end.
					Sc Cu below ^{heavier to east} multilayered cloud & aerosol structure to north.
094233	P4 ↓	12000ft			Sc Cu below, Larger Cu to North, still has aerosol layers visible.
094451	P4 ↓	10000ft			Some structure, starting to increase
094721	P4 ↓	7500			8
094854	P4 ↓	5500			abs 18, 200 scat, CO calibration
interrupt	P4.	5000			Interrupt for CO calib @ 5000ft.
					Loss of data to Flight Manager screen.
					Clear below
Recommers	P4 ↓	5000			
095310					Transient neph peaks
095420	P4	4000			neph green SO, CNC 5840
095424	R2.1	4000			O ₃ 74, CO, 132, NO, SO ₂ 5.25
					NOx 0.96
095751	R2.1	4000			Peaks in
					Sc Cu below, Some Ci & Alt ^{above,}

In pollution layer
O₃ 72, CO 132, SO 95

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
100138		4000			Cumulus below & around
100158					Cloud, lumpy neph
100405		4000			4x7000ft Pollution layer [noted pilot suggests 5000ft for return leg)
100445		4000			Clear below, Ci & contrails above.
100736		4000			little organic Sulphates or nitrates AMS
100952	^{end} R2.1	4000			Clear below Clear below, Ci above Neph's flat??
101107	^{start} R2.2	4000			Neph's back? clear below, Ci above Cu to west
101622	R2.2	4000			Clear below, power station to right.
102050	R2.2				Over sea, clear below, clear Ci & contrails above.
102135	R2.2				Passing Lido!
102329	^{end of} R2.2	4000			Neph & CO low
102329	P3A				Profile to 5000 to switch pilot set
102439	P5end				End of profile
103359	R3.1	5000ft			Start run over sea, Ill to Lido clear below, Ci above
103900	R3.1				Calix neph again.....

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.045**.....

 Date**29/8/04**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
104037	R3.1	5000ft			Wp back? CO 110, O ₃ 58, Neph reading -ve on Horace
104245	R3.1	5000			clear below. Very hazy. Ci above. (5/8) Cu to North
104846	end of R3.1				Clear below, Clear at above
105019	R3.2	5000			
105346	P6	5000 ↓ 3000 ↓			Cloud ahead 4-7000 ft. Bumpy descending
105632	P6	3000			Bumpy - convection, running below cloud base, hopping in 2nd pollution layer @ CO rising
105632	R3.2	3000			Bumpy, clear below, Sc Cu above
110147	R3.3	3000			Cu @ 20000, ppb higher but more variable ascent.
110423					NOx high, camp max high scat, high conc. Green scat 195 m ⁻¹ CNC 91000
110511	R3.3	3000			End of run
110753					NO channel off bottom
110820	R3.4	3000			CO 144, O ₃ 69 ppb clear below, Ci above C-Δ
111100	R3.4	3000			RH 94.6%
					Blank plots on Horace, numbers updating

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
111418	R3.4	3000 gh			O ₃ 66, CO 129, neph still somewhat elevated
111626	R3.4				RH 94%
111626	R3.4	3000			In cloud??
111859	R3.4	2800 3000			CNC 8600, RH 89%
					O ₃ 68%, CO, 139, clear below
112120	R3.4	3000			Bumpy, clear below. Two distinct layers to the RHS of plane with clear/draught cloud level
112204	R3.4	3000		(Point D?)	CO 123, O ₃ 68, neph 52 RH 84 CNC 5220
112414	R3.5	3000		D → E	End of 2nd plane, with diff neph blue/red ratios??
112617	R3.5	3000			CNC 6910,
112908	R3.5	3000			Bumpy, clear below 2 poll layers clearly vis 2 north lower one thick below cloud, upper one less distinct.
113214	R3.5	3000			Apparent correlation between turbulence & PCASP → thermal updrafts mixing plumes?
113343		3000			Bumpy Cu, up to ~7000ft just to N CNC 10000
113612	R3.5	3000			PCO & neph all diminishing sharply CO 138, neph 174.
113655	R3.5	3000			

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.045**.....

Date29/08/04.....

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plume
chemical
aerosol
noted in
turn

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
113844	Turning			turning over part E	Turning over motorway & some high ground. CO 171, O ₃ 75, raph 184 CNC 10300 RH 89%
114054	P7↑	3000ft	E→D	E→D	clear below, Hags Cu to North extending ↑ 7000ft Sc Cu around & above
114301	P7↑	6000ft	E→D		ScCu below, pollution layer below cloud visible to North. Upper pollution layer very thin but ~ 8000 ft. Look on way down.
114908	P7↑	FL1100	E→D		Scattered Cu below, largely clear above.
115335	P7↑	FL150	D		Peaks observed in CO, O ₃ etc just at point D @ top of profile
115832	P8↓	FL150	D→C		Cham calib finished
120024	P8↓	FL130	D→C		Few scattered Cu below. largely clear above. Towing Cu (~8000ft) ahead to north. CO 75, O ₃ 40
120337	P8↓	FL100	D→C		extensive Sc Cu below.
120559	P8↓	FL70	D→C		Cu below
120942	P8end	3000ft		C	Bumpy, clear below, convection
121113		3000ft			Bumpy CNC 39900, CO 143 143, O ₃ 77, RH 89%

Core chem
calib ideal
conditions.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

50-3000 → FL511
500 per min
6 + 12 = 15 mins

Flight No **B.045**.....

Date **21/08/04**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121247	R4.1	3000ft	C-B		Clear below Sc Cu above
121330	4.1	3000ft	C-B		over motorway
121601	4.1	3000ft			PCASP 1500; CN 20000
					Neph green 89 RH 92%
					7/8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ nitrate
					5- Sulphate
					6-7-11- organic
					ammonium buffered
12:2153	4.1	3000ft			Clear below Sc Cu above
					Ground fire on Left of cockpit
122323	4.1	3000ft.			uncorr $w = 0.87$ PSAP front panel
122419	4.1	3000			Bumpy. Convection quite strong
122754	4.1	3000			Clr below, agricultural, Cu above
122959	4.1	3000	B		Core chem calib, inside turn
123131	R4.2	3000	B-A		Core chem still calibrating
123546	R4.2	3000			several small/medium ground fires to North of flight path (ie @ 0'clock!!)
123829	R4.2	3000			Passing powerstation @ 3pm pos
					Haze in distinct layer above us
					wind 2ms^{-1} 240 deg.
124039	R4.2	3000			Over sea. Clear below.
					Ci e contrails to east
					Spikes in Neph and slature in CO_2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B045

Date: 29/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:12:59	300		0	10							Start Profile 1 from 5000'
08:14:48	220			8							4000'
08:16:20	130			8							End of Profile 1 @ 3000'
08:18:46											Start Profile 2 from 3000'
08:20:01											End of P2 start of Run 1.1 @ 4000'
08:21:00	220		25	8							
08:23:00	180			8							
08:25:00	200			8							
08:27:00			Overheat								
08:28:09											End of Run 1.1
08:29:42											Start Run 1.2 @ 4000'
08:30:00	220			10							
08:32:00	200			10							
08:34:00	200			8							
08:36:00	400			8							
08:38:00	260			8							
08:40:00	300			8							
08:42:00	200			8							
08:44:00	380			8							
08:46:10											End of Run 1.2
08:48:15			On								Start Run 1.3 @ 4000'
08:49:00	580		25	8							
08:51:20	180			8							
08:53:00	200			10							
08:55:00	260			10							
08:57:00	220			10							
08:59:00	220			10							
09:01:00	210			10							
09:02:58											End of Run 1.3
09:05:09											Start Run 1.4 @ 4000'
09:06:00	260			10							
09:08:00	200			10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B045

Date: 29/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:10:00	130		25	8							
09:12:00	110			8							
09:14:05	80			8							
09:16:00	70		26	8							
09:18:00	400			8							
09:19:38											End of Run 1.4
09:23:03											Start Profile 3 from 4000'
09:24:30	590			15							FL050
09:25:30	700			20							FL060
09:26:33	70			5							FL070
09:27:40	25			5							FL080
09:32:35	40			2							FL130
09:34:20	40			2							End Profile 3 @ FL150
09:39:36	HEATER	ON									Start Profile 4 @ FL150
09:40:41	90			2							FL140
09:41:33	20			3							FL130
09:42:37	100			2							FL120
09:43:41	130			2							FL110
09:44:43	80			2							FL100
09:45:49	70			2							FL090
09:46:49	85			2							FL080
09:47:35	70			2							FL070
09:48:25	900			10							FL060
09:49:28	800			10							FL050
09:54:24	250			10							End of P4 Start Run2.1 @ 4000'
09:55:00	260			10							
09:57:00	240			10							
09:59:00	400			10							
10:01:00	200			8							
10:03:00	150		27	8							
10:05:00	330			20							
10:07:00	220			15							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B045

Date: 29/8/04

Operator: MAP

Page 3 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:09:00	200		27	10							
10:09:52											End of Run 2.1
10:11:07											Start Run 2.2 @ 4000'
10:12:00	350			10							
10:14:00	230			10							
10:16:00	145			10							
10:18:00	310			10							
10:20:00	350			15							
10:22:00	330			15							
10:23:22	300			15							End of Run 2.2 Start P5 from 4000'
10:24:44	180			10							End of Profile 5 @ 5000'
10:34:04											Start Run 3.1 @ 5000'
10:35:00	280			10							PCASP HEATER OFF
10:37:00	270			10							
10:39:00	260		28	10							
10:41:00	305			10							
10:43:00	500			20							
10:45:00	340			15							
10:47:00	270			10							
10:48:15											End of Run 3.1
10:53:00											Start Profile 6 from 5000'
10:53:59	180			10							4000'
10:55:26	600			10							End of Profile 6 @ 3000'
10:57:48											Start Run 3.2 @ 3000'
10:58:00	800			15							
11:00:00	1200			10							
11:02:00	1400			10							
11:04:00	900			10							
11:05:16											End of Run 3.2
11:08:23											Start Run 3.3 @ 3000'
11:09:00	700			10							
11:11:00	900		Overheat	10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B045

Date: 28/8/04

Operator: MAP

Page 4 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:13:00	1400			10							
11:15:00	750			10							
11:17:00	1200			10							
11:19:00	900			15							
11:22:07											End of Run 3.3
11:24:14											Start Run 3.4 @ 3000'
11:25:00	160			15							
11:27:00	260			15							
11:29:00	200			15							
11:31:00	230			15							
11:33:00	160			15							
11:35:00	1000			20							
11:37:00			ON								End of Run 3.4
11:40:52											Start Profile 7 from 3000'
11:42:07	290		28	15							FL040
11:43:16	310			10							FL050
11:44:18	100			5							FL060
11:45:20	60			5							FL070
11:46:16	300			5							FL080
11:47:17	270			10							FL090
11:48:16	75			1							FL100
11:49:20	15										FL110
11:50:25	5										FL120
11:51:20	10										FL130
11:52:36	10										FL140
11:53:36											End of Profile 7 @ FL150
11:58:32	HEATER	ON									Start Profile 8 from FL150
11:59:50	40			1							FL140
12:00:37	15			1							FL130
12:01:43	30			1							FL120
12:02:39	50			1							FL110
12:03:34	80			1							FL100

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B045

Date: 28/8/04

Operator: MAP

Page 5 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:04:20	190		28	5							FL090
12:05:15	130			2							FL080
12:06:00	90			2							FL070
12:06:46	230			5							FL060
12:07:41	210			5							FL050
12:08:40	1500			10							FL040
12:09:37	680			10							End of Profile 8 @ 3000'
12:12:48											Start Run 4.1 @ 3000'
12:13:00	890			10							
12:15:00	1200			10							
12:17:00	700			10							
12:19:00	750			10							
12:21:00	410			10							
12:23:00	140			5							
12:25:00	150			5							
12:27:00	170			5							
12:29:00	140			5							
12:30:00											End of Run 4.1
12:31:32											Start Run 4.2 @ 3000'
12:32:00	300			15							
12:34:00	310		29	15							
12:36:00	380			15							
12:38:00	370			10							
12:40:00	370			10							
12:42:00	240			10							
12:44:00	240			10							
12:44:30											End of Run 4.2
	PCASP CH1,2,3 u/s										
	SEADAS Tape time offset = +3										

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	29/8/04	Flight	B 045
Operator(s)	A. Wilson		Campaign	ADRIEX	
Departure	29 075808 Z		Arrival	29 130000 Z	

Physical system setup

Module Number Serial	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0	SWS NIR
27581	SWS VIS

System functionality check After system stabilizes

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0 secs	at time	062600 Z
Freezer temp				

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 045	Date	29/8/04	Operator(s)	A. Wilson	log page	1	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

072930			90°A			DARK CURRENT VIEW.			
074300						DATA START			
074500						VIDEO RECORD.			
075808				Auto		TAKE OFF!			
075924			0°			Sample period 1 second.			
081256	P1	050-010							
081616	P1	030		Auto		end at 030.			
081846	P2	030-040							
082001	P2			Auto		End @ FLO40			
082001	R1	040	0°			Point A → B			
082040						PC Clock advanced 1 minute to tie in with aircraft time. *			
082909	R1			Auto		END			
082942	R1.2	039	180°			Point B to C			
	R1.2			Auto		End @ C			
084815	R1.3	040	0°			C to D			
090303	R1.3	040	0°			end @ D			
		040	180°	Auto					
090509	R1.4	040	180°	Auto		D to E			
091938	R1.4	040	180°	Auto		End @ E			
092303	P3	040	0°	Auto		Profile 3 040 → 150			
093419	P3	150	0°	Auto		end P3 @ Point D.			
093936	P4	150	180°	Auto		Profile P4 FL150 → FL040 to point C			
095424	P4	040	0°	Auto					
	R2.1	040				Point C to B.			
100952	R2.1	040	0°	Auto		end @ Point B			
101107	R2.2	040	180°	Auto		Point B to A.			
	R2.2	040				End @ Point			
	P5	040-050							
102441	P5	050		Auto		end P5			
103404	R3.1	050	0°	Auto		A to B			
104816	R3.1	050	0°	Auto		@ Point B			
104945						Video stop			
104957						Video start (new cassette)			
105300	P6	050-030	180°			Profile to 030 to escape cloud.			
105632	P6	030	180°			end of P6 @ FL050			
105748	R2.3	030	180°	Auto		180° B to C			
110516	R3.3	030	180°	Auto		@ Point C			
110823	R3.4	030	0°	Auto		C to D			
112207	R3.4	030	0°	Auto		End @ Point D			
112325		030	180°	Auto		min int period set to 10ms.			
112414	R3.5	020	180°			D to E			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B045	DATE: 29/08/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: Po Valley, N Italy		PROJECT: ADRIEX – flight to investigate pollution in the Po Valley, Italy	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	N2	Argon/CO2	CO
PRE FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar
POST FLIGHT	1280 psi / 122 bar	2370 psi / 162 bar	720 psi / 50 bar

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)		
28/08/04 12:55:33	FL050	R7	90.77	61.13	5549.01	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: last calibration data from previous flight for comparison with today.													
29/08/04 ::	ground	-				-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: First cal of day. Air sample pipe closed.													
05:18:55	ground	-	83.43	56.18	4687.01	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: ASP closed.													
07:03:46	ground	-	84.42	66.52	5615.79	684.749	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: ASP closed.													
07:31:08	ground	-	80.85	69.17	5592.47	186.569	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 502-537													
07:38:27	ground	-	80.42	69.66	5601.74	203.066	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 521-526													
07:53:46	ground	Taxiing	86.44	68.36	5908.38	183.941	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: ASP closed. Post power changeover/reboot cal. CO cal max values : 565-590													
07:58:37	ground	taxiing	82.58	69.59	5746.92	189.330	40	0.99	3.87	4.86	5.75		
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.78	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.61	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.78	PMT °C
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 499-504 Take off acceleration began a few seconds before end of cal.													
08:08:23	FL050	-	81.12	70.16	5691.17	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	Flow Lamp:	33.87	Press Monocr	0.75	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.60	Lamp °C	-	Monocr °C	-	PMT °C
Remarks: Air sample pipe now open. CO cal max values : 514-518													
08:21:00	FL030	> P2	81.38	70.24	5715.97	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: CO cal max values : 525-530 Climb/P2 started half way through cal to get above cloud. Levelled at FL040 before end of cal.													
08:26:20	FL040	R1	81.33	70.02	5694.69	110.262	62	0.11	0.53	0.63	5.09		
Remarks: CO cal max values : 524-527													
09:38:08	FL150	-	83.90	65.08	5459.84	93.278	63	-0.02	0.21	0.19	6.93		
	Flow Lamp:	33.85	Press Monocr	0.70	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.57	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.41	PMT °C
Remarks: Post P3													
09:52:20	FL050	-	83.86	66.34	5563.66	144.198	80	0.03	1.15	1.18	5.19		
Remarks: Cal started 09:49:24 CO cal max values : 524-530 Interrupt to P? @ FL050 for CO cal.													
10:51:47	FL050	-	83.10	65.52	5444.24	119.278	59	-0.02	0.83	0.80	5.37		
	Flow Lamp:	33.82	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.61	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.70	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 516-520													
11:58:24	FL150	-	85.41	61.71	5270.77	97.210	63	-0.12	0.30	0.18	6.89		
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 537-541												
12:33:25	FL030	-	87.19	61.32	5346.26	135.172	67	0.02	1.14	1.16	4.84		
	Flow Lamp:	33.44	Press Monocr	0.78	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.62	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.88	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 534-539 Cal started at end of R4.1 (12:29:58)													
::	FL										-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks:													
::	FL										-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks:													
::	FL										-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks:													
::	FL										-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks:													

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...045

Date ...29.8.04.....

Page ...1... of ...2...

Video Tapes		GPS	INU	DRS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
(V8)		Lat	45 39.18N	45 39.16N
No. # 1.		Long	12 12.06E	12 12.06E
Ends 1108		Time	07 44:28	07:44:07
FFC / RFC / (DFC) / (JFC)		Status	✓	NAV.
				HORACE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
				SATCOM <input type="checkbox"/>

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GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
074310	INU to	NAVIGATE						
075859	TAKE OFF	FROM TREVISO.						
	ATC restrictions mean no run @	1000ft.						BAP avg 10s. → 30s
	UBBR covers off.	0620						
090303				AB, BC, CD, D → E				Explorer lost flt sum
090509	Start Run	1.4	D → E					
091938	End Run	1.4						
092303	Start Profile	P3						
		4000ft						→ FL150
093936	Start	P4						
094926	Int	P4 @						5000ft.
095308	Recon	P4						↑
		Level at 5.						for Cals
095424	End Profile	4 @						4000ft / Start Run 2.1 @ Charlie
	End Run	2.1 @						Bravo, 4000ft.
		inside turn then next runs @						5000ft.
	Start Run	2.2						B → A @ 4000ft.
	End Run	2.2 at						Alpha. / Start P5
102441	End	P5						5000ft.
103404	Start	Run 3.1						A → B
104816	End	Run 3.1						Bravo
	Start	Run 3.2						B → C 5000ft
105300	Start	Profile						6 ↓

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B.045**.....

Date **29.8.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS			FFSSP		
Satcom C			PCASP		
Satcom H			2D-P		
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C		
De-Iced Temp			Cloudscope		
Non De-Iced			SID 1		
Heimann			SID 2		
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI		
G. Eastern			HVPS		
J. Williams			<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov			INC		
TWC			CCN / CNC		
FWVS			CVI		
<u>Radiometers</u>					
Upper Clear			<u>Aerosol</u>		
" Red			PSAP		
" Silicon			Nephelometer		
" JO1D			AMS		
Lower Clear					
" Red					
" Silicon					
" JO1D					
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS					
MARSS					
DEIMOS					
ARIES					
SWS / SHIM					
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone					
ECGC					
NOX					
CO			<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC					
PAN					
PERCA					
WAS					

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. 8045

Instruments

1. PSAP - output voltages don't tie in with cal
2. Neph - after t/o, all signals at. -0.91E-6m^{-1} . Sw off/on, no better. Do cal then okay.
3. UFC - debris ^{or smudge?} on lens.
4. Explorer error on clicking ok on Update Fitsum. No server. close index, Plot + Fitsum + re open e then ok. Plot window comes up with 0's for all the data
5. A/c scientist horace display not displaying
6. Neph - strange values after cal, reset 100949 and again 10:21:05 - Readings all -0.91 .
7. Aft Cor Con CB panel - GE CB v. sticky

Aircraft

Intercor - Aft Cor Con can't hear corchem.

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Lot of breakthrough from flight deck (IRR training).

Text display for **SATCOM**

00099 29-AUG-04 12:21:12 728 LATEST POSN RPT RECD..

LATEST POSN RPT RECD..

No weather information available for LIPH,.

No weather information available for LIPR,.

LIPZ VENICE TESSERA (Elev. 7 ft - 0mb) VCE

Today 29/08/04 Sunrise 04:32 Sunset 17:48 UTC

METAR

LIPZ 291150Z VRB03KT CAVOK 26/18 Q1016=

LIPZ 291120Z VRB03KT CAVOK 26/20 Q1016=

LIPZ 291050Z VRB03KT CAVOK 26/19 Q1016=

LIPZ 291020Z VRB02KT 9999 FEW020 BKN220 26/19 Q1016=

TAF

LIPZ 291100Z 291221 13005KT 9999 FEW030 SCT080=

E - Exit P - Prev

H - Step>